

SPECIAL

**Scalable Policy-awareE Linked Data arChitecture for
prlvacy, trAnsparency and complIance**

Deliverable D4.3

Transparency dashboard and control panel release V2

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SPECIAL DELIVERABLE

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1 Introduction

The goal of work package four (WP4) is to provide data subjects with a privacy dashboard that serves as a control panel for them to access and assess their personal data a controller and possible additional processors, they are concerned with, process for a variety of purposes. Furthermore, data subjects shall be able to rectify or erase inaccurate data, review given consent, or withdraw it. All these actions require interaction and communication with the respective controller. The privacy dashboard is supposed to ease this interaction and communication by defining concrete tasks and actions that can be triggered by the data subject or controller and by structuring information required by the controller to act upon the data subject's requests. This way data privacy concerns can be easier expressed, transmitted, processed, and automated by defining business processes in accordance with existing laws.

New legal requirements imposed by the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)¹, which came into effect in May 2018, emphasize the significance of privacy-enhancing technologies such as privacy dashboards. Article 5 of the GDPR defines multiple personal data processing principles such as *lawfulness* and *fairness*², *purpose limitation*³, *data minimization*⁴, *accuracy*⁵, *storage limitation*⁶, *integrity and confidentiality*⁷, and *accountability*⁸. We argue that the transparency principle⁹, which is newly introduced in Article 5 of the GDPR, requires innovative approaches to realize this personal data processing principle. Due to its vague expression in the legal text, controllers and processors are left in uncertainty when it comes to required actions that need to be taken to be compliant with this principle. Moreover, it is not possible to provide data subjects with transparency by simply showing them all their personal data the controller processed of them. The vast amount of information and the frequency in which it is processed will overwhelm the majority of data subjects. To provide data subjects with the right information they require to express reasonable data privacy decisions is the key challenge of WP4.

For this reason, activities in WP4 address research and user studies in particular in the fields usable privacy, data visualization, consent management including alternatives for privacy policies and innovative consent interfaces, policy expression of access and usage policies, and the general research fields privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) and transparency-enhancing tools (TETs).

WP4 started at month nine of the project, i.e. September 2017, and this deliverable is written and submitted in month 25 of the project, i.e. January 2019. The first version of this deliverable (D4.1 Transparency dashboard and control panel release V1) was submitted in month 16 of the project, i.e.

¹ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), OJ L 119, 4.5.2016, p. 1-88 [hereinafter GDPR]

² GDPR art. 5(1)(a)

³ GDPR art. 5(1)(b)

⁴ GDPR art. 5(1)(c)

⁵ GDPR art. 5(1)(d)

⁶ GDPR art. 5(1)(e)

⁷ GDPR art. 5(1)(f)

⁸ GDPR art. 5(2)(a)

⁹ GDPR art. 5(1)(a)

April 2018. Version 2 of the deliverable extends Version 1 and documents our efforts taken since the beginning of WP4 until now to fulfil the tasks **T4.1 Transparency dashboard and control panel** and **T4.2 Consent engine and feedback mechanism**. During that time, we developed a first prototype for the dashboard that was evaluated within a first user study and multiple consent interfaces that are currently evaluated via multiple user tests.

The remainder of this document is structured as follows: in Chapter 2 the objectives and overall scope of WP4 are discussed, followed by a description of the scope of this deliverable. In Chapter 3 concepts are presented and discussed. Subsequently, Chapter 4 presents the developed prototype of the dashboard, and the chapters 5 and 6, which present multiple approaches for consent interfaces. Finally, a summary and conclusion are given including an outlook on the planned next steps.

2 Goals and scope of the dashboard

This target of this chapter is to extend the introduction by formulating, defining, and narrowing the objectives of the dashboard, which embody the overall scope of WP4. The following subsection gives details on how these objectives are addressed and approached in WP4. Last, the scope of this deliverable will be defined.

2.1 Overall scope of WP4

Figure 1 depicts a mind map of the *so-called transparency dashboard and control panel* (in the following only *dashboard* or *privacy dashboard* for simplicity reasons) derived from the SPECIAL proposal. Therefore, keywords used in the proposal have been extracted and classified into functional components of the dashboard (colorized green) and general attributes or requirements of the dashboard (depicted in red squares). Based on Figure 1, the objectives of the dashboard are discussed in the following individually.

Figure 1: A mind map of the transparency dashboard and control panel derived from the SPECIAL proposal.

2.1.1 Functional components

ACCESS DATA

The dashboard's main purpose is to offer data subjects an interface to access and assess their personal data that is processed by a single or multiple controllers and processors within a specific context for various purposes. We argue that, in order to be compliant with the GDPR, controllers must introduce, develop, or adapt privacy dashboards. Biere et al. (Biere et al. 2016) formulate the same assumption. Data privacy rights like the right to rectification or the right to erasure require data subjects to access and assess their personal data. This includes in particular all personal data not just the information that the data subject deliberately and fully aware disclosed to the controller, but also data obtained from other sources like third parties (such as advertising networks for example), data measured by

sensors (in particular Internet of Things devices), information provided by the data subject in publicly available online profiles (Facebook, LinkedIn, and suchlike), and inferred information gained from Big Data applications. While all this information needs to be made accessible to the data subject, it is also of importance to make it digestible for the data subject. Providing access to the data does not necessarily imply transparency, thus a strong focus on usability needs to be laid.

EVENT LOG/ PROVENANCE

In addition, meta information and provenance data are needed to provide full transparency to the data subject. This includes the purpose and the legal basis of the processing, involved processors, context information like time and the physical location of the processing servers, and which safeguards are applied to protect the data subject's personal data. In deliverable **D1.3 Policy, transparency and compliance guidelines V1** (Section 3.1) a complete list of provided information can be found. The specification of the event logs data format is part of work package two (WP2) and is described in deliverable **D2.3 Transparency Framework V1** in detail. The event log's visualization and the identification and presentation of the relevant and necessary information are major challenges addressed in WP4.

ACCESS AND USAGE POLICIES

The expression of access and usage policies is a core functionality of the privacy dashboard. However, the underlying policy language SPECIAL introduces in WP2 (see deliverable **D2.1 Policy Language V1**) goes beyond conventional access control systems, since legal requirements of the GDPR shall be expressed and formulated with it. This way, SPECIAL aims to enable automated compliance checking with the GDPR. Violations of the GDPR could be prevented in real-time during the processing of personal data. WP4 will offer data subjects an interface to express policies in various forms, thus, a withdrawal of consent for a specific purpose will be reflected with the policy language, so the data subject's withdrawal can be applied (almost) immediately. The same applies for the right to rectification, erasure, or object. WP4 will avoid complex interfaces with many options, so data subject's will not be required to understand the policy language at all, while still using it.

POLICY TEMPLATES

To reduce even more complexity, policy templates are offered to data subjects. Research (Liu et al. 2016) shows that users can benefit from so-called privacy recommendations in order to enhance their data privacy. The definition of those privacy recommendations depends heavily on the context of the controller, the purpose of the processing, and the data subject's privacy preferences. Thus, the definition of reasonable policy templates is a central challenge of WP4, which will be evaluated in user studies to find out if policy templates really ease the complexity of privacy policies and decisions.

CONSENT ENGINE

The consent engine is another core component of the dashboard. It is supposed to allow data subjects to review consent that was previously given, to give informed consent for additional purposes offered by the controller, and to withdraw consent if necessary. WP4 pursues two main goals: (i) designing and implementing consent interfaces that make consent actually (and measurably) informed, (ii) and furthermore, find mechanisms to prevent data subjects being "scared away" by consent requests, for example by informing about the risks and highlighting the benefits of the data disclosure. Therefore, we plan to address and reflect the *privacy calculus theory* (Dinev and Hart 2006) in our consent interfaces.

BREACH NOTIFICATION

The breach notification is a new legal requirement of the GDPR obliging controllers to properly inform data subject's in case of a data breach. Its significance is emphasized by recent data breach incidents like the Equifax case¹⁰ or the Cambridge Analytica and Facebook scandal¹¹. As stated in the introduction, the dashboard's intention is to ease and structure interaction and communication between data subject and controller. In case of a data breach, data subjects can be provided with the most relevant and urgent information and recommendations to react upon data breaches. Controllers might benefit from a standardized, uniform, and automated mechanism enabling them to be compliant with the GDPR. WP4 aims to identify the relevant information data subjects need and how this can be presented in a usable and user-friendly way.

2.1.2 General requirements

PERFORMANT AND SCALABLE

The dashboard must be performant and scalable, this means, it must be capable of handling a vast amount of data, while keeping response times within a reasonable time range. To achieve this, stress tests with unrealistic amounts of data will be conducted. Additionally, mechanisms will be implemented that limit the amount of data displayed. This also contributes to the usability of the dashboard. An asynchronous execution environment enables the application of techniques like lazy-loading to optimize response times on a fine-grained level.

SECURE

The dashboard must be secure since it is used to access sensitive personal data. The security risk involved by introducing the privacy dashboard (as an additional mean to access personal data) must be limited to an absolute minimum. The highest degree of security can be achieved by deploying the dashboard within the controller's domain, this way, the data subject's personal data remains in its entirety within the controller's infrastructure. Only small chunks that the data subject wants to review are transmitted to his or her local machine. For this transmission state-of-the-art encryption techniques are used that offer the highest possible security. Data retrieved by data subjects will be deleted after every session or encryption at rest¹² is applied to secure the data on the data subject's machine from access by possible malicious software.

PRIVACY-ENHANCING

It must be privacy-enhancing to an extent that the introduction of a new security risk is justifiable. Data subjects must be able to use it to fulfil tasks that actually enhance their data privacy. These tasks do not only have to be fully implemented, but also the definition of these tasks is crucial. What tasks within the context of their data privacy do data subjects expect and need in order to make decisions that positively affect their data privacy?

¹⁰ Equifax Suffered a Hack Almost Five Months Earlier Than the Date It Disclosed - Bloomberg. <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2017-09-18/equifax-is-said-to-suffer-a-hack-earlier-than-the-date-disclosed>, last accessed: 04/16/2018.

¹¹ Facebook and Cambridge Analytica face class action lawsuit - The Guardian. <https://www.theguardian.com/news/2018/apr/10/cambridge-analytica-and-facebook-face-class-action-lawsuit>, last accessed: 04/16/2018.

¹² Encryption at Rest | Google Cloud. <https://cloud.google.com/security/encryption-at-rest/>, last accessed: 04/26/2018.

USABLE

It must be usable by a variety of user groups and types in order to serve the purpose as a transparency-enhancing tool and privacy-enhancing technology. As already stated above, providing transparency is not trivial. Transparency is enabled by granting access to the data, but still requires a usable and user-friendly presentation so data subjects can interpret and comprehend the impact of the presented information on their data privacy.

2.2 Scope of D4.1 and D4.3

To narrow the scope of this deliverable, the description of D4.1 and D4.3 in the proposal is used, besides the above given explanation of WP4. The deliverable is described in the proposal as follows:

“This release will include policy and event data visualisation (T4.1) and system interaction (T4.2).”

- Description of D4.1 in the proposal

“This release includes improvements to the policy and event data visualisation (T4.1) and system interaction (T4.2) and new visualisations to support the transparency and compliance functionality (T4.1 & T4.2).”

- Description of D4.3 in the proposal

Therefore, it is helpful to cite the descriptions of tasks **T4.1 Transparency dashboard and control panel** and **T4.2 Consent engine and feedback mechanism** at this point.

“An interactive dashboard will provide end users with a digestible log of what happened with the data based on the provenance/event data. In the context of our use cases, the dashboard will be specifically tailored to cater for these Big Data traits. The tool will also enable users to verify that data processors and data controllers are complying with both access and usage policies and with the data protection legislation. Given the volume of data involved, the dashboard will be highly intuitive and flexible, making it easy for the user to pull data based on different contexts. Particularly, the dashboard will allow for checking policy templates in terms of legal requirements (cf. T2.2) but also other easy to understand and re-use “canned” policies in the form of policy templates, developing a kind of “Creative Commons” scheme for end-user policies.”

- Description of T4.1 in the proposal

“One of the challenges faced by our use case partners is the fact that much of the data they currently possess can’t be used because they do not have the consent to do so. The consent engine feedback mechanism, which will be embedded into the dashboard, will provide the data subject with the ability to highlight data that is inaccurate and to specify new or update existing access/usage policies.”

- Description of T4.2 in the proposal

Based on the descriptions of the tasks, we include in this deliverable a first prototype of the SPECIAL privacy dashboard and multiple prototypes for consent interfaces. Our prototypes aim to address all components of **Section 2.1**.

3 Concepts & design decisions

This chapter presents and discusses theoretical concepts for the privacy dashboard and the consent interfaces with the aim to make the designs and different approaches more comprehensible. For this reason, the chapter is separated into two subsections.

3.1 Concepts for the privacy dashboard

As stated above, the visualization of data is a major challenge for the design of the dashboard and a central concern of WP4. The main question is, whether a uniform design for a user interface for all kinds of controllers and data subjects is realistic or not. An alternative would be to build a specific privacy dashboard for every controller and for every user group or type. So, in a first step it is reasonable to identify factors that the appearance of the privacy dashboard depends on. See Figure 2 for an overview.

Figure 2: Identified factors that the privacy dashboard’s appearance depends on including principle requirements like usability, legal, or business requirements.

In general, the appearance of the privacy dashboard depends heavily on the controller and its domain. Most controllers have a dedicated branding that customers expect to see whenever they interact with the controller. The so-called corporate design is a central building block of the corporate identity, that helps users identifying and verifying the controller’s “*identity*” in application scenarios in which no real persons are present (like the Web). The branding is an important requirement that should be taken into consideration when developing the prototypes because it massively influences the appearance of the privacy dashboard.

Legal requirements are derived from the legislation, which to some extent depends on the domain of the controller, since different business domains are subject to different regulations. WP4 only considers legal requirements from the GDPR.

Data subjects influence the privacy dashboard's design since their experience with computers and the Internet is a key factor for the usability of the privacy dashboard. In addition, data subjects vary in terms of age, education, and attitudes (towards privacy in particular), thus their priorities of relevance of information provided by the tool may differ. Furthermore, the user groups and types partially depend on the controller and its domain. Considering that Google, for example, concerns potentially all kinds of users including minors, whereas controllers like Tinder are only used by data subjects of legal age. These two user groups do not only differ in age but also in multiple other characteristics.

The tasks that the privacy dashboard is intended to fulfil is another key factor that its appearance depends on. The tasks and how they are executed determine whether a component like a button is needed or in which order components have to be aligned. These tasks also depend on the addressed user groups since different users may execute different tasks more often than others or execute some tasks not at all, while others on a more frequent basis.

The personal data in question massively influences the appearance of the privacy dashboard. Its subject, context, and domain determine what is displayed and how. What kinds of data categories are displayed also depends on the controller and its domain. The tasks and how they are executed mainly influence the way the data is displayed. For example, if data subjects just want to review location data the address in plain text may be sufficient, whereas the rectification of a location information may be easier for data subjects to realize on an interactive map with a marker.

Figure 3: A wizard-like design that guides data subjects through a series of questions leading them to the desired information or action.

Figure 4: A graph visualizing what information was processed and combined and what information has been derived from that combination.

The identified factors shall help to classify different design approaches. We designed examples for task-centric design approaches (see an example in Figure 3) that put the focus on the tasks data subjects want to fulfil and data-centric design approaches (like depicted in Figure 4) that lay focus on the data itself and emphasize meta information within the context of the processing. User-centric design approaches analogously address the data subject's needs, while controller-centric design approaches are very controller-specific designs that address particular privacy matters of a controller and its data subjects. Controller-centric designs could be realized within existing user interfaces of the data controller's service, without introducing a new and dedicated component for privacy matters.

3.2 Consent interfaces

SPECIAL aims to design and implement new and innovative consent interfaces that enable data subjects to give actual informed consent, while at the same time strengthening their confidence in data disclosure and information sharing with controllers and processors. This appears to be a contradiction intuitively. User studies (Lai et al. 2006) confirm that users, when asked, tend to disagree with data disclosure for purposes like tracking or profiling. However, studies addressing the extensively researched privacy calculus theory (Dinev and Hart 2006) suggest that data subjects are willing to share their information when offered something in return.

Purposes of processing personal information are categorized into two categories: (i) user features and (ii) personal data processing. The first category consists of functional features the data subject desires to use like photo upload, photo sharing, video upload, video sharing, and suchlike. The second category contains purposes that primarily serve the data controller such as profiling for targeted advertising, tracking to improve profiling techniques, or requesting additional external data sources for information of the data subject. For giving consent to one of the purposes in the second category, data subjects retrieve points they can spend to "get" the user features they desire. The purposes and their value are determined by the data controller beforehand.

This is a very experimental approach with open expectations for results. However, it seems very promising and worthwhile pursuing to investigate this approach. The controller's interests to get explicit and informed consent for privacy-critical purposes like profiling and location tracking are

considered and addressed in this design. On the other hand, data subjects have actual control on a finer-grained level. The current modus operandi is “*all-or-nothing*”, i.e. data subjects either must agree with the privacy policy and use the service or disagree with the privacy policy and not use the service at all, although they might agree with the majority of personal data processing practices of the data controller (Steinfeld 2016). It is furthermore imaginable, that this approach leads to more informed consent since data subjects will aim to maximize what they can get for their “earned” points, thus being aware what they consented to and what not. To confirm this assumption, user studies are needed.

This principle is also used to define policy templates that can be offered to data subjects in a pricing table like manner, which represent different privacy plans the data subject can choose for this service. Conceivable profiles include for example: *most privacy preserving/ limited functionality*, *moderate data disclosure/ full functionality*, and *maximum data disclosure/ premium functionality*.

To compare this approach with more familiar consent interfaces that rather meet the expectations of data subjects regarding giving informed consent, alternative interfaces are designed and implemented that aim to reduce the amount of text needed to communicate the contents of a controller’s privacy policy to the data subject. Here, giving consent remains a statement represented by ticking a checkbox. These approaches can suffer from the “all-or-nothing” paradigm; however, they might be well suited to inform data subject about data processing practices and involved privacy risks.

Since these concepts offer different levels of control to data subjects, a combination of all of them is conceivable and reasonable. Data subjects that feel their preferred privacy setting is not represented by any of the policy templates might want to “customize” consent by earning and spending points. Analogously, data subjects who want to give consent based on precise information and on a very fine-grained level might use a familiar consent interface that offers more text and less interactivity.

3.3 Dynamic consent

One goal of SPECIAL is to rethink and redesign giving consent to personal data processing entirely. In Section 3.2, we described concepts for innovative consent interfaces that keep the general approach of asking for consent during the service subscription. This approach has many disadvantages, which lead to users giving uninformed consent. Besides the sheer amount of text that privacy policies consist of, the contemporary irrelevance of most of its content hinder users from carefully reading through the privacy statement. Moreover, even if doubts arise from reading the privacy policy, there is no mean to express, communicate, or negotiate them with the controller.

Privacy policies cover all data processing scenarios, however, not all scenarios are equally relevant to all users. Often it is also dependent on the user’s usage of the service. A user, for instance, might not use a certain feature of a service at all. Therefore, one might argue that it is more reasonable to ask for consent when the processing of personal data becomes necessary in order to fulfil the user’s requests. Similar to how the mobile operating systems iOS and Android ask users for permission to access certain resources of their smartphone, when the user is about to use a certain feature that makes access to a certain resource necessary.

We introduce our concept of dynamic consent in SPECIAL. See Figure 5¹³, for an exemplary application of dynamic consent in an event recommender use case. We identified three phases around the concept

¹³ Access online via <http://dashboard.specialprivacy.eu/Storyboard.png> for full size.

of dynamic consent: *notice*, *transparency*, and *control*. Dynamic-consent-enabled services need to communicate this novel approach to their users during the subscription for the service. Otherwise, the constant sending of consent requests would collide with the user’s expectations. Therefore, the first phase should focus on giving notice.

Notice

Transparency

Control

Figure 5: Storyboard for the concept of dynamic consent regarding the user interface

The main phase is called transparency, since the user should be aware (or at least able to be aware) of any data processing during that phase. Despite the user benefitting from enhanced transparency, we found this phase as a challenge for the user. We assume personal data processing to occur often and

in a high frequency. Thus, consent requests would be sent to the user at the same rate. Likely, users are not willing to undergo such cumbersome process only to protect their privacy. For this reason, we designed strategies to massively reduce the number of consent requests to a minimum.

The main strategy is assuming consent is given, when the user does not respond to a consent request. This is not really conforming with the privacy-by-default paradigm but does not differ too much from today's reality of personal data processing. However, our approach only behaves in the described way, if the user is in a privacy-sensitive context (e.g. the user is in a table dance bar). This requires the system to detect such a privacy-sensitive context. To achieve this, linked data and semantic web technologies are used. When the user is in such a situation, all consent requests that are sent to the user during that time are rejected by default. Additionally, users are able to define certain situations (in our case areas or locations) by themselves in which consent requests are rejected by default.

Another strategy is to learn from past user decisions. The system can remember user decisions and with the help of statistical analysis determine certain combinations, which always led to a certain decision. For example, could a user always reject consent requests that involve location data stored outside of the EU. Or users consent to almost anything that involve a specific purpose. For such occasions, the consent request could be hidden and only indicated with an icon. This way the user would be able to see that personal data is currently processed, but, if concerned with other things, not be bothered with it.

Apparently, both approaches hold potential for errors. Therefore, the user must be able to make corrections when necessary. For this reason, we introduce the phase control. There needs to be a user interface the user can address privacy concerns to. Here, the user must be able to review all consent requests and their decisions (whether there were done by the user or the system). Withdrawing consent must be fast and easy, since the user might want to make multiple corrections.

4 Transparency dashboard and control panel

This chapter presents the previous and current state of the privacy dashboard developed during the last 16 months since the begin of WP4 in month 9. The prototype has been developed as a Web application realized with Hypertext Markup Language (HTML), Cascading Style Sheets (CSS), and JavaScript using the JavaScript framework *React*¹⁴. To adapt state-of-the-art design principles for such kind of applications and to ease the process of styling, *Google's Material Design*¹⁵ guidelines were followed. Therefore, the React library *material-ui*¹⁶ has been used. In the following screenshots and corresponding descriptions will be given to describe the prototype textually. Both versions, the previous state of the privacy dashboard (<http://raschke.cc/SPECIAL-privacy-dashboard-V1/>) and the most current version of it (<http://dashboard.specialprivacy.eu/>) are published on the Internet.

4.1 Status of the privacy dashboard as of D4.1

This section presents the previous version of the privacy dashboard as of **D4.1 Transparency dashboard and control panel release V1**, which was submitted in month 16 (April 2018).

Figure 6: The previous version of the privacy dashboard structured into three-columns.

As it can be seen in Figure 6, we have decided to follow a rather user-centric (also data-centric) design approach. In the left sidebar (see Figure 10 for a bigger image), data subjects find filter options to reduce the amount of presented data. Its intention is to ease the navigation through the data subject's personal data, which is assumed to be extensively large. Besides filtering personal data based on its data type and time of its processing, we consider the context of its processing. We therefore defined

¹⁴ React - A JavaScript library for building user interfaces. <https://reactjs.org/>, last accessed: 04/16/2018.

¹⁵ Material Design. <https://material.io/>, last accessed: 04/16/2018.

¹⁶ Material-UI. <http://www.material-ui.com/>, last accessed: 04/16/2018.

data categories that have been derived from Bruce Schneier's data taxonomy (Schneier 2010), which he defined for online social networks. Here follows a short description of Schneier's data taxonomy:

- **Service data** is any kind of data that is required in order to provide the service in question (name, address, payment information).
- **Disclosed data** is any data that the data subject intentionally provides on their own profile page or in their posts.
- **Entrusted data** is any data that the data subject intentionally provides on other users' profiles pages or in their posts.
- **Incidental data** is any kind of data provided by other users of the service about the data subject (a photo showing the data subject posted by a friend).
- **Behavioral data** is any kind of data the service provider observes about the data subject while he or she uses the service (browsing behavior).
- **Derived data** is any kind of data derived from any other category or data source (profiles for marketing, location tracks, possible preferences).

To adapt this data taxonomy for all kinds of domains, we removed the social network context. Based on the results of a user study, we merged the data categories *Service data*, *Disclosed data*, and *Entrusted data* into a single data category (***Intentional data***). Our resulting data taxonomy is presented below:

- **Intentional data** is any piece of data the data subject deliberately discloses to the controller fully aware of the disclosure.
- **Incidental data** refers to information relating to the data subject shared by another entity with the controller.
- **Behavioral data** is any data obtained from monitoring the data subject's behavior regardless of his or her awareness of the monitoring.
- **Derived data** is any information derived, inferred, or obtained from the other categories or combination of them.

The data is presented in the middle of the screen ordered chronologically beginning with the "oldest" entry from the top to the bottom. Each data item has its own visual representation, which gives information on the time of its processing, a description and explanation of the processing, the data category it belongs to (represented by an icon) and the data itself. As can be seen in Figure 7, for each data entry a submenu can be opened with one click, which reveals the purpose of the processing and offers possibilities to withdraw consent for the purpose and rectify or erase the data in question. A grouping of data items with regard to the time is reasonable and was already presented in **D4.2 Usability testing report V1**.

Figure 7: Representation of each data item by a visual component that gives context information on the processing.

Figure 8: The withdrawal of consent is represented through a predefined written notice that is sent to the controller. The message can be edited by the data subject.

Withdrawing consent, requesting rectification, or erasure actually are legal requests that have to be responded by the controller within a certain time according to the GDPR¹⁷. Although it is a goal of SPECIAL to automate the application and realization of these requests, a formal notice is sent to the controller, which documents the request and the deadline for the controller to respond to the request (see Figure 8 for an example of such a message). The deadline is determined in an automated way. The dashboard can help data subjects to manage deadlines of their data privacy requests enabling them to keep track of pending requests and identify lapsed deadlines. This requires an overview of messages sent to the controller, which can be seen in Figure 9. Messages are categorized into pending and answered requests. Here, the data subject can review sent messages and the answers of the controller to his or her request. Further requests and responses to answers from the controller can be sent as well.

¹⁷ GDPR art. 12(3)

Figure 9: A message section gives an overview of pending and answered requests.

Figure 10: The left sidebar offers data subjects to filter the presented personal data. The right sidebar gives information on the controller in question.

Figure 10 shows the right sidebar that gives general information on the respective controller. General information to contact the controller either physically (name and address) or digitally (email address) are given. A link to the controller’s privacy policy might help data subjects to even find the privacy policy (they probably consented to, when registering for the service). The option **Review consent** leads to the consent interfaces. The controller component of the dashboard needs further attention in the next iteration to identify, which information is relevant to data subjects with regard to the data controller.

The dashboard will be further evaluated in multiple user studies with different user groups and types. The results of these user studies will be included in the deliverables **D4.3 Transparency dashboard and control panel release V2** and **D4.4 Usability testing report V2**.

4.2 Current status of the privacy dashboard

This section presents the current state of the privacy dashboard as of month 25 (January 2019). With the second release of the privacy dashboard we enhance the event log visualization and address the functional components: access and usage policy, policy template, and consent engine (see 2.1.1). Besides visual improvements Version 2 also aims to give users a broader view on the data the controller processes, the kind of processing that is executed, the processors involved, and the physical location of the controller's and processor's servers.

Figure 11: A screenshot giving an overview of Version 2 of the privacy dashboard.

As it can be seen in Figure 11, we abandoned the simple three column approach, and give the most relevant information on the controller (including the controller's logo, the name, a description, an email address, and the controller's website) at the top of the page. The timeline of processing events was moved to another tab to directly present the user with statistical information on the controller's processing practices. Tables and (rather) simple charts are used to provide the user with an overall picture of the controller's personal data processing practices. We therefore define the following four questions, we consider most important for users, who use the privacy dashboard:

1. What data is processed and for what purposes?
2. What kind of processing took place and which data was used?
3. Where is data stored and with whom was it shared?
4. Where is which data stored?

Each question is supposed to be answered separately in a so-called card with the help of table and charts. The statistics shall provide an overall picture without being too specific. Therefore, the relatively broad data categories of the SPECIAL vocabulary suit quite well. The cards are supposed to confirm (or not confirm) user expectations. Users might expect that a location-based service, for instance, processes location data predominantly, while processing no health data at all.

Figure 12: A card to give the user general information on processed data and for which purposes it is processed.

Figure 12 shows the first card, which gives information on the kind of data that is processed by the controller and the purposes for which the controller processes personal data. On the left-hand side, the top five processed data categories are listed in a table sorted by their amount of the total processing logs. On the right-hand side, a pie chart is given to visualize the amounts of processing logs with regard to the processing purpose. Here, all purposes that appear in the processing events logs are visualized regardless of how small their overall amount might be. It is important to note, that there is no correlation between both visualizations, i.e. there can be, for example, no statement made on whether the (roughly) 20% of activity data (in Figure 12) are evenly used for all purposes or only used for one of the purposes.

In contrast to that, Figure 13 shows correlations between processing types and data categories used for the processing. For each processing category, the corresponding data categories are stacked according to their amount of processing events with that specific processing type. From that diagram it can be for instance inferred that more than one fifth of the data that is anonymized is activity data or that approximately one fifth of the data that is aggregated is audio-visual activity data.

Figure 14 and Figure 15 are similar to Figure 12 and Figure 13. They aim to provide the user with information on the physical location of servers on which the user’s personal data is stored. Besides the physical location the SPECIAL vocabulary also addresses the sovereignty of these servers. Is the controller fully in charge or are other parties involved? Who retrieves my personal data and which privacy practices do these third-parties have? These questions are not answered by the card (Figure 14) but a general tendency is given. When in doubt because the chart does not address the user’s expectation, then the user is able to further navigate in the privacy dashboard to answer those questions.

Figure 13: A bar chart to visualize correlations between kinds of processing and categories of data.

Figure 14: A card to give users an impression of where their data is stored and what kinds of third parties retrieve it.

Figure 15: This chart gives information on where which kind of data is stored.

Figure 16: Improved visualization of processing events in the timeline.

In the previous version of the privacy dashboard there was a processing event log entry foreseen for each data item that was processed. This led to many visual repetitions of timeline entries, which are interdependent (see Figure 6 and Figure 7). Moreover, we expect the frequency of processing events in some use cases to be very high, thus many events need to be considered. Therefore, further grouping of those events is desirable (see also **D4.2 Usability testing report V1**). The data categories of Section 4.1 are not compatible with the SPECIAL vocabulary, hence the filter options of the previous version were removed. Now, events can be grouped by **purpose**, **data** category, kind of **processing**, the **recipient**, or the **storage location**.

Each timeline entry (card with pink header as in Figure 16) gives information on personal data processing within a certain time range. A textual summary is given to list which data categories were processed for which purposes, where stored, and with whom shared. Depending on the grouping criteria another card (within the timeline card) is given to give more specific information. This card can be extended to see the corresponding processing events for which a textual visualization is given. The submenu of the previous version (see Figure 7) is also included in the most recent version.

GENERAL INFORMATION TIMELINE **POLICIES**

Policies of Proximus use case

There are 2 policies for this application.
Application code: 9940460e-e003-4cbb-9e58-db790909f405.

The controller is able to collect your **audiovisual activity and location** data for **marketing** purposes.
It is stored in **the controller's servers** and was shared with **the controller, legal entities that act as the controller's agent or vice versa**.

Description: Proximus policy #2

The controller is able to collect your **audiovisual activity** data for **marketing** purposes. It is stored in **the controller's servers** and was shared with **the controller, legal entities that act as the controller's agent or vice versa**.

You gave consent to this policy.

Description: Proximus policy #1

The controller is able to collect your **location** data for **marketing** purposes. It is stored in **the controller's servers** and was shared with **the controller, legal entities that act as the controller's agent or vice versa**.

You gave consent to this policy.

Figure 17: Under the policies tab the user can view the controller-specified policies and update consent to them.

By opening the policies tab, the user is able to see all controller-specified policies. Furthermore, the user is able to see to which policies he or she consented to and if necessary is able to withdraw consent for a single or multiple policy. Policies are in relation to an application of the controller; therefore, policies are grouped by their respective application. One problem of this view is that if a policy is in relation to multiple applications it would be visualized multiple times. However, it is thinkable that the user might give consent to a policy for a certain application but not for another. Figure 17 also shows the textual representation of a single policy or a set of policies.

5 Consent engine and feedback mechanism

The developed consent interface prototype designs are presented in this chapter. As stated above, we developed multiple consent interfaces that offer different degrees of control to the data subject. The approaches are presented and discussed individually starting with the privacy plans approach, followed by the customizable consent approach, the broad consent with reduced complexity, and last the dynamic consent approach.

5.1 Approach: Privacy plans

Giving consent to the personal data processing practices of a particular service of a data controller is usually realized by ticking a checkbox labeled with a text that is somewhat similar to *“I’ve read and agree to the privacy policy”*. Ticking the checkbox is supposed to imply that the data subject has read, understood, and agrees with the privacy policy of the controller. The privacy policy itself contains relevant information about the types of data processed, for what purposes it is processed, and with whom it is shared. The GDPR binds given consent to a specific purpose, thus emphasizing the significance of the purpose. This design approach, presented in Figure 18, addresses the significance of the purpose, while (currently) neglecting all other information of the privacy policy. It is therefore an experimental approach, which possibly is not sufficient at the moment to meet legal requirements for informed consent. Following iterations will address this issue.

Less data disclosure / basic functionality	More data disclosure / advanced functionality	Most data disclosure / maximum functionality	Custom disclosure / and functionality
Features	Features	Features	Features
Publishing texts <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Publishing texts <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Publishing texts <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Publishing texts <input type="checkbox"/>
Photo upload <input type="checkbox"/>	Photo upload <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Photo upload <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Photo upload <input type="checkbox"/>
Video upload <input type="checkbox"/>	Video upload <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video upload <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video upload <input type="checkbox"/>
Voice messaging <input type="checkbox"/>	Voice messaging <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Voice messaging <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Voice messaging <input type="checkbox"/>
Location sharing <input type="checkbox"/>	Location sharing <input type="checkbox"/>	Location sharing <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Location sharing <input type="checkbox"/>
Location-based recommendations <input type="checkbox"/>	Location-based recommendations <input type="checkbox"/>	Location-based recommendations <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Location-based recommendations <input type="checkbox"/>
Personal data processing	Personal data processing	Personal data processing	Personal data processing
Authentication <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Authentication <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Authentication <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Authentication <input type="checkbox"/>
Logging <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Logging <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Logging <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Logging <input type="checkbox"/>
Profiling <input type="checkbox"/>	Profiling <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Profiling <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Profiling <input type="checkbox"/>
Location tracking <input type="checkbox"/>	Location tracking <input type="checkbox"/>	Location tracking <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Location tracking <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="button" value="APPLY"/>	<input type="button" value="APPLY"/>	<input type="button" value="APPLY"/>	<input type="button" value="APPLY"/>

Figure 18: Data privacy plans to easily and quickly choose a privacy setting that reflects the privacy preferences of the data subject.

As already explained in Chapter 3, purposes for processing personal data are defined by the data controller and categorized into **Features** and **Personal data processing**, while the first category represents functionalities the data subject intends to acquire and the second category comprises personal data processing practices that the controller mainly benefits from. Figure 18 shows three data

privacy plans and a forth option to customize a plan on a finer-grained level. The three plans are in this case: **less data disclosure/ basic functionality**, **more data disclosure/ advanced functionality**, and **most data disclosure/ maximum functionality**. These plans are supposed to be predefined by the data controller who is aware of technical requirements that need to be considered at this point but also is given the chance here to formulate acceptable compromises. For example, the controller cannot offer the data subject location-based recommendations without processing the physical location of the data subject. Or the controller is only willing to provide the data subject with features like photo and video upload and voice messaging only if being allowed to profile the data subject.

User studies are supposed to show whether data subjects are willing to accept such consent interface as a formal and legally valid means to consent to the processing of their personal data. Moreover, this prototype misses relevant information that would be part of the privacy policy but are currently not included in this design. It would be interesting to investigate the best way to define these data privacy plans and which privacy plans are chosen more frequently than others and why.

5.2 Approach: Customized consent

If the data subject has chosen to configure a customized data privacy plan, he or she is presented the consent interface depicted in Figure 19. As explained in Chapter 3, consenting to purposes of the category **Personal data processing** could “earn” the data subject points that can be “spent” to acquire features. The values are supposed to be predefined by the controller as well. This way more control can be offered to the data subject but limited by the individual values for the purposes to implicitly address the controller’s interests.

Data disclosure	Functionality
Personal data processing <input type="checkbox"/>	Features 0
Authentication +50 points <input type="checkbox"/>	Publishing texts -100 points <input type="checkbox"/>
Logging +50 points <input type="checkbox"/>	Photo upload -100 points <input type="checkbox"/>
Profiling +600 points <input type="checkbox"/>	Video upload -200 points <input type="checkbox"/>
Location tracking +1000 points <input type="checkbox"/>	Voice messaging -300 points <input type="checkbox"/>
	Location sharing -500 points <input type="checkbox"/>
	Location-based recommendations -500 points <input type="checkbox"/>
	EXPERT MODE APPLY

Figure 19: Consenting to purposes (that the controller benefits from) allows data subjects to “get” features they desire.

The current prototype does not meet the legal requirements neither and would need to be extended to meet legal requirements of the GDPR. However, it is conceivable that this design encourages more data disclosure (with reference to one of the goals of WP4). Figure 20 shows a configuration with “unspent” points that the data subject might consider using (by consenting to **Photo upload** for example). This design approach gives personal data a concrete counter value. However, it has to be carefully evaluated whether data subjects perceive this interface and the interaction with it as giving consent. Reviewing the situation in Figure 20 again, it is questionable whether all data subjects

understand that they implicitly allowed the data controller to obtain and process their physical location by “acquiring the purpose **Location sharing** (despite not consenting to the purpose **Location tracking**).

Figure 20: A custom configuration allowing data subjects to consent to the processing of their physical location without allowing the controller to track their location or give location-based recommendations.

5.3 Approach: Broad consent with reduced complexity

Figure 21: A mobile consent interface guiding data subjects through multiple views, which explain in detail what kind of data is used for which purposes.

This section presents and reports on the activities regarding the concept of broad consent with reduced complexity. Therefore, we first present the results as of D4.1 followed by the results as of D4.3.

5.3.1 Consent interfaces as of D4.1

Due to today's popularity of mobile devices like smartphones and the changed user interaction mechanisms, the above presented design approaches might not be best-suited for these kinds of devices. Furthermore, these approaches are very experimental and break the mental paradigm of users who currently need to agree with a privacy policy by clicking a checkbox. For this reason, this design approach tries to communicate the contents of a privacy policy more efficiently with regard to the length of texts and space that can fit on a screen. Addressing mobile devices in particular contributes to the overall goal to reduce text and complexity of privacy policies to make these more comprehensible and thus more accessible to data subjects. Figure 21 and Figure 22 show two variants of the mobile interfaces both with similar mechanisms to provide the least amount of information possible, while informing data subjects as much as possible.

These interfaces need to undergo an evaluation from a legal perspective and further user studies to evaluate their usability. However, it could be that these interfaces perform rather well since they are closer to familiar consent interfaces. The main challenge therefore in next iterations is to identify the limits of such interfaces. Studies shall reveal how much information can be communicated with these interfaces and at which points are users overwhelmed by the amount of information.

Figure 22: A mobile consent interface consisting of a single view and components that can be clicked or tapped to retrieve more information and to consent to the individual personal data processing practices.

5.3.2 Consent interfaces as of D4.3

Figure 23: Mobile consent interfaces as of D4.3 developed for the Proximus use case

Since giving consent is a secondary task for the user, the actual service offered to the him or her (the reason the user is asked to give consent) needs to be addressed in the interface design and considered in the evaluation of these user interfaces. For this reason, a start screen was developed, which displays actual events around a certain location (e.g. the user's location). By clicking on one of those (indicating interest) the user asked to sign up for the service including giving consent.

Here, the options offered to the user were reduced. Besides the approach to give consent for each data category (see Figure 22), the user shall be primarily able to configure whether he or she wants to retrieve personalized event recommendations or not. This way, an almost anonymous usage of the service is possible. Users who desire personalized events currently cannot make further adjustments, however we will combine the two versions giving users a third option (e.g. **custom personalization**), which enables them to give consent for each data category as in Figure 22.

5.4 Dynamic consent

In this section, we describe our first prototype for the dynamic consent interfaces. This current state of the prototype covers the notice phase at the moment. However, we plan to address the other phases with our next release. Figure 24 shows the first two screens the user is presented with. They are supposed to explain the benefits of the service to the user and how and why the service wants to personalize the user experience. Figure 25 shows an example consent request to make the user familiar with the approach and the user interface that is used to give consent. We designed the consent request in a heads-up notification, since it is rather visible, when the smartphone is used, yet disappears rather quickly in case of no user interaction.

Figure 24: The first two screens of the Finder subscription explain the service and the personalization method.

Figure 25: An example consent request is given during the subscription to explain the interface to the user.

Figure 26: At last an explanation of the next steps is given to the user.

In Figure 26, the last screen of the service subscription is depicted. After the user has been made familiar with the dynamic consent approach, the set-up is completed. Afterwards the user is regularly asked by the consent engine for consent. In the final release, we will include a fully working prototype of the dynamic consent approach, which covers all three phases.

6 Consent control interface

In this chapter, we first review the requirements of the GDPR concerning informed consent and the background information about the dynamic consent requests. Then we describe our exemplifying use case scenario and the user interface wireframes for the dynamic consent request that we created based on this use case. In the end of the section we provide details on the interactive wireframes for the dynamic consent request that we developed to be tested with the help of the user study.

6.1 Introduction

Before discussing our versions of the user interface (UI) for the informed consent request, let us recall the background information about consent request that our UIs are based on (cf. D1.3 Policy, transparency and compliance guidelines V1).

In the GDPR the processing of personal data is prohibited via Art. 6 except for some predefined scenarios (e.g.: public interest¹⁸, legal obligations¹⁹) and when the data subject has consented²⁰ to his or her personal data processing. According to Art. 4, the consent of the data subject should be: (i) freely given; (ii) specific; (iii) informed and with unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes; (iv) given by a clear affirmative action by which he or she signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her²¹. Although it is highly dependent on the concrete use case, the main information that must be presented in the consent request to the data subject is:

Data. What data (data categories) are processed?

Purpose. What is the purpose of data processing?^[L]_[SEP]

Processing. How are the data processed?

Storage. Where and for how long are collected data stored?

Sharing. With whom are the data shared?

In **D1.3 Policy, transparency and compliance guidelines V1** we identified the need for **dynamic consent** instead of a ready-made, set in stone, static consent forms. Depending on the context, our dynamic consent could have all or some of the following features:

Categorization. The dynamic consent request groups similar requests into categories and asks for consent once per category.

Customization. More control is given to the user by providing a possibility to choose what data he or she allows to be processed, for what purpose, where those data can be stored and, if he or she allows data sharing - with whom.

Innovation. The user has an option of consenting to very general data processing for such purposes as service optimization and business intelligence.

Historical Data. The list of purposes could include processing of data subject's personal data that were gathered at some point in the past.

¹⁸ GDPR art. 6(1)(e)

¹⁹ GDPR art. 6(1)(c)

²⁰ GDPR art. 6(1)(a)

²¹ GDPR art. 4(11)

Revocation. The data subject should be able to withdraw his or her consent for future processing and sharing of all (or a part) of his or her data at any time.

Understandability. The consent request should be presented in an understandable way, so that the data subject understands the implications of his or her consent.

6.2 Use case scenario for the consent request UI

For the development our consent request UIs we used the exemplifying use case scenario introduced in **D1.3 Policy, transparency and compliance guidelines V1:**

Sue buys a wearable appliance for fitness tracking from BeFit. She is presented with a dynamic informed consent request, comprised of a data usage policy that describes which data shall be collected, why they are collected, how they will be processed, stored and shared in order to give her fitness-related information.

For the purpose of our research and analysis we made the use case more specific by adding the exemplifying concrete data flow (see Figure 27) where we describe what data are collected by BeFit for what purpose and sub-purpose, where the collected data are stored and for how long, how those data are processed, what data are shared with third parties and what third parties are involved. Although the dataflow we use for our use case (and, as a result, also for our UIs of the consent request) is simplified, it is clear from Figure 27 that increasing data in the graph will increase its complexity. For the purpose of the initial development of the UI wireframes (creating a skeleton of our UI) and subsequent user studies there is no need for a highly complex use case. Scalability can be tested later in the course of the UI development.

Figure 27: The information that must be presented to the data subject in BeFit's consent request.

6.3 Dynamic consent request UI wireframes

Based on our discussions with the consortium partners, we decided to create different versions of the UI wireframes for the dynamic consent request to be tested with users to find how they perceive those UIs and what improvements could be made. We drafted three possible UI wireframes, namely graph, tabs, and user agent to be reviewed in one of our consortium meetings. All of them have features of the dynamic consent request as well as fulfill the requirements of the GDPR, in terms of the main information that should be presented to the user.

6.3.1 The Graph

The first UI wireframe is in the *graph* form as in Figure 27. The graph should be interactive allowing users to customize the consent and to withdraw their consent at any point in time. Figure 28 depicts one of the ways how the possibility to give consent could be implemented. The data subjects could choose any element of the graph. After the element is chosen, the button “Allow” would appear in the selected element.

Figure 28: Possibility to give consent by clicking “Allow” button in the selected element of the graph.

The users should have an option to give their consent selectively. Figure 29 shows a possible option to present unique paths to the user, so he or she can decide what exactly to consent to.

Figure 29: View of the unique path that could help the user to see what exactly he or she would be consenting to.

The graph also provides a possibility to withdraw the consent, or a part of it, at any point in time and as easily as it was given. Figure 30 depicts the consent withdrawal for the graph wireframe. The consent is withdrawn in the same way as it was given: the user selects an element and clicks, in the case of withdrawal, the button “Deny”.

Figure 30: Possibility to withdraw consent by clicking the „Deny“ button in the selected element of the graph.

The representation of consent information in a graph form has its pros and cons. The advantages of the graph lie in (i) the possibility of showing all the relations between purpose, data, storage, processing and sharing, (ii) giving good feedback to the user about what he or she has already consented to. The disadvantages of the graph approach are that, even with such a small amount of data to be visualized as in our use case, it can cause an information overload for the data subject. Another disadvantage of this approach is that it is difficult to adapt the graph for every display size without the need for scrolling.

6.3.2 Tabs

The second UI option is to represent data in more familiar way in the form of *tabs* (Figure 31). Here the user can browse the following tabs: data (what data are processed), purpose (what is the purpose of data processing), processing (how are the data processed), storage (where and for how long are collected data stored), sharing (with whom are the data shared). The user can customize his or her consent by turning on (giving consent) or off (withdrawing consent) the switchers opposite, in our example, the list items of the data tab. Users can also use the icons next to the switcher to create more fine-grained customization. There could also be an integrated video that provides users with an overview of the information on each page.

Figure 31: Dynamic consent request in the form of tabs.

The tabs UI has flexibility, can be made responsive and is not complex at first sight, so the data subject will not be discouraged from using the service. However, it is difficult to highlight what data were selected by the user, so the user can get lost easily and it is hard for him or her to know when he or she finished giving the consent.

6.3.3 Agent

The third UI version for the dynamic consent request is the one with an *agent* and pop-up speech balloons (Figure 32). As two other versions, this UI also aims to provide all the dynamic consent features relevant to our use case and the main information about the data processing.

Figure 32: Dynamic consent request with an agent.

Similar to the UI with tabs, this UI is not complicated at first glance, but, here, as well, there is no good indication of what the user has already read. This UI version is not well suitable for every display size. The agent UI received the least positive feedback when presented to the consortium. However, there was positive reaction for usage of the agent UI on demand, for example, when there is a need for user's consent for a new purpose or a new data category.

6.4 First interactive UI wireframe for the dynamic consent request

Since we wanted to involve real data subjects at the early stage of the UI development, we decided to prepare a user study in order to test the UI functionality, content placement and intended page behavior of one of the UI versions. Based on the feedback from the consortium partners and colleagues in the UI field of research, we decided to take the tabs UI as the basis for our first interactive wireframe but enrich it with the graph UI. The graph UI has limited functionality and its main purpose is visualization of unique paths the user can give his or her consent to. Figure 33 depicts our wireframe of the first UI version for BeFit's dynamic consent request. We would like to stress that this UI is just the first version, we plan to test other versions later in the course of the project.

To make our wireframe more realistic and more suitable for user studies, we developed its fully functional online version²². While creating this online version we followed Jakob Nielsen's usability heuristics for user interface design²³. We used Angular Material²⁴ and D3.js²⁵ for the front-end development of the online version and Firebase²⁶, with its real-time database and hosting, for the server side.

Figure 33: The wireframe of the first version of the dynamic consent request UI.

²² BeFit | Consent Request. <https://cr-wizard-en.firebaseio.com/wizard>, last accessed: 01/30/2019.

²³ 10 Heuristics for User Interface Design: Article by Jakob Nielsen. <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/ten-usability-heuristics/>, last accessed: 04/16/2018.

²⁴ Angular Material. <https://material.angular.io/>, last accessed: 04/16/2018.

²⁵ D3.js - Data-Driven Documents. <https://d3js.org/>, last accessed: 04/16/2018.

²⁶ Firebase. <https://firebase.google.com/>, last accessed: 04/16/2018.

Our first online interactive wireframe was developed based on the features of dynamic consent request from D1.3 adapted to BeFit's use case scenario. This wireframe provides the following functionality:

Categorization. We grouped information according to five categories, namely purpose, data, storage, sharing and processing. This grouping is realized in the form of tabs (Figure 34). In the tab *purpose*, we display the services that are offered by BeFit and that require personal data processing. The tab *data* lists personal data that could be processed by BeFit, if the data subject consents to data processing. In the *storage* tab we provide information on where BeFit stores data subject's personal data. The *sharing* tab gives insights into third parties with whom BeFit may share personal data of the data subject. In the *processing* tab we describe how personal data could be processed. To support the visualization, additionally to the name of the category on the tab, we added icons for each category.

Figure 34: Categorization in the form of tabs (purpose, data, storage, sharing, processing).

Customization. The most important feature of our first version of the consent request UI is the full customization of data subject's consent. We do not offer an all or nothing approach. The user can fully adjust his or her consent specifically to his or her wishes. Our consent request gives the possibility to review information or give consent according to five categories mentioned in the categorization feature above. Any tab category can be a starting point of giving consent. The user is also given a possibility to drill down a concrete path and agree only to that path. This means that the data subject can also give permissions to process only specific data categories for chosen purposes, etc. For example, he or she can allow BeFit to process his or her resting heart rate (*data*) to be displayed to him or her in BeFit's app (*purpose*) by performing on-device calculations (*processing*) and saving his or her data on his or her device (*storage*) without *sharing* it with anybody. The drill down feature is implemented by placing clickable icons of possible drill-down options near each item in the category/tab list (Figure 35). The user can drill down each item in the list by clicking on an icon that corresponds to the category he or she wants to select. In this way the user can create a unique path to consent to. The unique path is displayed and can be navigated in the breadcrumb under the tabs (Figure 35). The user gives his consent just by selecting checkboxes that correspond to his or her preferences. The check box is placed near each category item after the icons for drill-down options (Figure 35).

Figure 35: Customization of data subject’s consent.

Innovation. As described in **D1.3 Policy, transparency and compliance guidelines V1**, one of the possible features of the dynamic consent is innovation – i.e., the user could help foster innovation by consenting to very general data processing for such purposes as service optimization and business intelligence. The purpose “*improve service provider’s products and services*” is included into the list of purposes in our consent request (Figure 36).

Figure 36: The purpose “improve service provider’s products and services” is included into the consent request to foster innovation.

Revocation. The user can withdraw his or her consent by removing the selection in any checkbox at any time (Figure 37). In our use case the consent is given for the first time before using the device and

the consent withdrawal in our interactive UI wireframe is tailored to this use case. If the user changes his or her mind later, he or she can use privacy dashboard for consent revocation.

Figure 37: Consent withdrawal by removing the selection in the relevant checkbox.

Understandability. To increase understandability and ease of use of the consent request we are using plain language and standard icons for the content. Every action of a user is backed up by feedback. To help the data subject to understand the implications of his or her consent, our dynamic consent request is supported by a graph (Figure 38). The graph has a tree form and shows every possible unique path that goes through the selected item. The paths that the user consented to are highlighted in red. Each item in the graph is represented with the help of already mentioned icons. More information, in the form of a tooltip, is shown upon hovering over each icon.

Figure 38: Graph could help the data subject understand the implications of his or her consent.

The user can also enlarge the graph to full-screen size (Figure 39) by clicking the corresponding button in the lower right corner.

Figure 39: Full view of the graph.

After the user finishes consenting (by clicking “Complete Consent Request” button), he or she is presented with an overview of all the information that he gave his or her consent to be processed by BeFit (Figure 40).

Purpose	Data	Storage	Sharing	Processing
Display all day heart rate	Resting heart rate	On the device		On-Device calculations.
Derive race time predictions	Sleep Time	On the device		On-Device calculations.
Improve service provider's products and services	Sleep Time	On the device		On-Device calculations.
Derive race time predictions	Steps	On the device		On-Device calculations.
Derive calories burned	Steps	On the device		On-Device calculations.
Enable a recovery adviser to advise when to start the next workout	Steps	On the device		On-Device calculations.
Improve service provider's products and services	Steps	On the device		On-Device calculations.
Display route on map	GPS coordinates	On 3rd parties' infrastructures	Axiom	Axiom calculations.
Display route on map	GPS coordinates	On 3rd parties' infrastructures	Google	Google calculations.

Buttons: Back To Consent Request, Go To Questionnaire

Figure 40: Summary of all the information that the data subject gave his or her consent to be processed.

To check the usability of our UIs for dynamic consent request we are conducting user evaluations.

6.4.1 User evaluation

For the evaluation we selected a think aloud method (van Someren 1994, Seidman 2006, Charters 2003) where the participants are first presented with BeFit's use case and then they are asked to imagine themselves buying BeFit's wearable appliance for fitness tracking instead of Sue. The participants are then asked to activate the device and give their consent for the processing of their data by BeFit. In the beginning the participants complete a series of tasks of giving and withdrawing consent. After this exercise they just give their own consent, as they would have done this, if they bought the BeFit smart watch. The participants record their screen and their thoughts. Our online wireframe enables participants to give their consent from any place comfortable for them, making our user evaluation more realistic. In the end of the assignment each participant fills in a questionnaire providing us with their demographic data as well as their impression of our dynamic consent request UI. The questions of both questionnaires can be found in the annexes. Immediately after finishing giving the consent, the participants are also asked to type in everything they remember consenting to. Twenty-seven participants, who are between 16 and 35 years old, took part in our usability evaluation. Most of them graduated from high school and have either Information Technology or Education as their background. 63% of the participants are male and 37% are female. The participants consider themselves competent, proficient or experts in Internet surfing. The results of the evaluation were published in D4.2 Usability testing report V1. The results showed that the data subjects were overwhelmed with the consent information because they needed to read and understand all the details. So, there was a clear need for the simplification of the consent request and the reduction of the consent information details that are mandatory for the data subject to read. Based on the user study results, we developed an improved version of the UI to be further tested in our next user evaluation.

6.5 Second interactive UI wireframe for the consent request

Since the graph functionality was well received by the users in our first user evaluation, we decided to use the graph as the basis for our next version of the consent request UI. In our interactive wireframe²⁷ (see Figure 41) we added color-coding to the graph, as it was suggested by many participants in the user study. The short consent information is placed inside a "bubble" in the graph.

The second version of the consent request UI incorporated the following features of the dynamic consent request.

Categorization. The users liked the categorization of the consent information into purpose, data, storage, processing and sharing in the previous UI, so we kept this categorization in the second version of the UI.

Customization. The participants highly appreciated the customization and the flexibility of the consent request. However, they expressed their frustration with too many options. In our second UI prototype we kept the customization feature, but we reduced the options by presenting users with the list of available device functionalities. All other information is then just shown in connection to the selected functionality and if there are any optional items, they are separately highlighted, with a dashed line, in the graph path. If the data subject accepts the data processing for each functionality, the corresponding functionality is moved from the "Available Functionality" column to the "Accepted Functionality" column.

Revocation. Our prototype provides the possibility to withdraw consent by selecting functionalities in the "Accepted Functionality" column and clicking the "Revoke" button at the bottom of that column.

²⁷ BeFit | Consent Request. <https://concent-request.firebaseio.com/builder>, last accessed: 01/30/2019.

Figure 41: The wireframe of the second version of the dynamic consent request UI.

Understandability. Since the users liked the shortness, the plain language and the icons, we reused the consent text from the first version of the prototype.

Innovation. The option to foster innovation by consenting to data processing to "improve service provider's products and services" remained in the second UI prototype.

Since the user evaluation is in progress, the results are going to be published in **D4.4 Frontend Scalability and Robustness testing report V2**. However, we can preliminary (even before the detailed analysis of all user study results) see that the data subjects are still overwhelmed with the consent information. This means that further simplification of the consent request and the reduction of the consent information details, that are mandatory for the data subject to read, most likely will be needed.

6.6 Third interactive UI wireframe for the consent request

Since the users do not want to spend extra time on reading information in the consent request and they ask to simplify the customization feature, we developed the third interactive UI wireframe²⁸ (see **Figure 42**) for the consent request to simplify the consent request even more.

The third version of the consent request UI incorporated the following features of the dynamic consent request.

Categorization. We grouped the functionalities according to the main topic that they are addressing. For our use case we identified five groups: (i) health, (ii) map visualization, (iii) fitness adviser, (iv) back-up, (v) marketing & BI. We ordered them according to the popularity of the functionalities among users. The companies usually have statistics on which functionalities are the most popular among their customers, so they can easily put the groups in the correct order.

Customization. In our third UI prototype we kept the customization feature, but we again reduced the complexity by presenting users with the list of groups on the right side of the request and the available device functionalities on the left side. The users could preselect a group of functionalities by using the slider near the groups. All other information can be then shown on demand (by clicking "?" near each functionality) and in connection to the specific functionality.

²⁸ BeFit | Consent Request. <http://cr-slider.soft.cafe/en/> last accessed: 01/30/2019.

Figure 42: The wireframe of the third version of the dynamic consent request UI.

If the data subjects accept selected data processing (i.e.: checked checkboxes near each functionality), they click "Submit Preferences" button to give their consent.

Revocation. Our prototype provides the possibility to withdraw consent separately for each functionality by deselecting a checkbox near each functionality or in bulk by using the slider near the groups.

Understandability. Since the users liked the shortness, the plain language and the icons, we reused the consent text from the first version of the prototype.

Innovation. The option to foster innovation by consenting to data processing to "improve service provider's products and services" remained in the third UI prototype.

Since the user evaluation is in progress, the results are going to be published in **D4.4 Frontend Scalability and Robustness testing report V2**.

7 Conclusions & Future work

This deliverable presents the activities and efforts made within the context of WP4 of SPECIAL during the last 16 months since the beginning of WP4 in month 9. We addressed the two tasks **T4.1 Transparency dashboard and control panel** and **T4.2 Consent engine and feedback mechanism** which cover the transparency dashboard and control panel (called privacy dashboard or dashboard) and the consent engine and feedback mechanism. We therefore reviewed the proposal to formulate goals that define the scope of WP4 and derived the goal and scope of this deliverable from that. As goals of WP4 we identified functional components such as data access, policy expression and templates, consent management, and breach notification. We identified general requirements for the dashboard like performance, scalability, security, privacy, and usability. This deliverable addressed the functional components data access, policy templates, and consent management focusing on the general requirement usability. Deliverable **D4.4 Frontend Scalability and Robustness testing report V2**, which is due at the end of month 27, will focus more on the remaining general requirements, i.e. performance, scalability, and security.

We presented the second version of our prototype for the privacy dashboard and elaborated on its design. We presented multiple designs and prototypes for consent interfaces and dynamic consent, which we developed and partially evaluated in user studies during the last 16 months. There, we already highlighted the next steps needed to improve the prototypes with regard to legal and usability requirements. We plan to pursue the design approaches presented in this deliverable and further evaluate those in user studies. The results of those user studies will be included in **D4.4 Frontend Scalability and Robustness testing report V2** and reiterated in **D4.5 Transparency dashboard and control panel release final release**, which is due in month 34.

8 References

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9 Annexes

9.1 Demographic Data Questionnaire

1. What is your gender?

- Male
- Female

2. What is your age

- less than 16 years old
- 16-25 years old
- 26-35 years old
- 36-45 years old
- 46-55 years old
- 55 years and over

3. What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- Some high school, no diploma
- High school graduate, diploma or the equivalent
- Trade/technical/vocational training
- Some college, no degree
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Doctorate degree

4. What is (or was) your field of studies?

- Natural and Physical Sciences
- Information Technology
- Engineering and Related Technologies
- Architecture and Building
- Agriculture, Environment and Related Studies
- Health
- Education
- Management and Commerce
- Society and Culture
- Creative Arts
- Food, Hospitality and Personal Services

5. On average, how many hours per day do you spend on the Internet?

- Less than 1 hour a day
- 1-3 hours
- 3-6 hours
- 6-8 hours
- More than 8 hours a day

6. How would you assess your current skills for using the Internet?

- Advanced beginner
- Competent
- Proficient
- Expert

7. How easy is it for you to use computers?

- Very difficult
- Somewhat difficult
- Neither difficult nor easy
- Somewhat easy
- Very easy

8. What is your preferred device to browse the Internet?

- Desktop computer
- Laptop
- Tablet
- Smartphone

9.2 Usability Testing Questionnaire

1. What do you remember agreeing to?

- Data
- Sharing
- Storage
- Purpose
- Processing

2. Overall, how satisfied or dissatisfied are you with the consent request?

- Very satisfied
- Somewhat satisfied
- Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
- Somewhat dissatisfied
- Very dissatisfied

3. How likely is it that you would recommend the consent request to a friend?

- Not at all likely
- Slightly likely
- Moderately likely
- Very likely
- Extremely likely

4. What was your impression of the time it took you to complete the tasks?

- Too long
- Too long but it was worth while
- About the right amount of time
- It took less time than I thought it would

5. Which of the following words would you use to describe the consent request?

- Annoying
- Appealing
- Boring
- Clear
- Compelling
- Complex
- Confusing
- Cutting edge
- Dated
- Difficult
- Disruptive
- Distracting
- Dull

- Easy to use
- Effective
- Efficient
- Effortless
- Empowering
- Engaging
- Exceptional
- Familiar
- Fast
- Flexible
- Fresh
- Friendly
- Frustrating
- Gets in the way
- Hard to Use
- Helpful
- High quality
- Impressive
- Ineffective
- Innovative
- Inspiring
- Intimidating
- Intuitive
- Inviting
- Irrelevant
- Old
- Ordinary
- Organized
- Overwhelming
- Patronizing
- Poor quality
- Powerful
- Responsive
- Rigid
- Satisfying
- Slow
- Time-consuming
- Time-Saving
- Too Technical
- Unapproachable
- Unattractive
- Uncontrollable
- Understandable

- Undesirable
- Unpredictable
- Usable
- Useful
- Valuable

6. How well the consent request does meet your needs for privacy policy representation?

- Extremely well
- Very well
- Somewhat well
- Not so well
- Not at all well

7. Information on which tab or tabs did you find useful and informative?

- Purpose
- Data
- Storage
- Sharing
- Processing
- None

8. Which tab or tabs should be removed because they are useless and overcomplicate everything

- Purpose
- Data
- Storage
- Sharing
- Processing
- None

9. How understandable did you find the tree graph?

- Not at all understandable
- Slightly understandable
- Moderately understandable
- Very understandable
- Extremely understandable

10. How useful did you find the tree graph?

- Not at all useful
- Slightly useful
- Moderately useful
- Very useful
- Extremely useful

11. What would you suggest to improve the tree graph?

Leave a comment

12. What did you like most about the consent request in comparison to a traditional privacy policy?

Leave a comment

13. What's the easiest part about using the consent request?

Leave a comment

14. What's the hardest part about using the consent request?

Leave a comment

15. Was there anything surprising or unexpected about the consent request?

Leave a comment

16. What could be done to improve the consent request?

Leave a comment

17. How easy is the consent request to use?

Leave a comment

18. Which feature (or features) of the consent request are most important to you?

Leave a comment

19. Which feature (or features) of the consent request are least important to you?

Leave a comment

20. What might keep people from using the consent request?

Leave a comment